

ISAR Imaging in Sea Clutter via Compressive Sensing

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Abstract— We investigate the application of compressive sensing (CS) to inverse synthetic aperture radar (ISAR) imaging of moving targets. We present our results for a simulated target immersed in different levels of sea clutter. Comparison between traditional and CS approaches to ISAR imaging reveal that our based CS algorithm offers some advantages compared to traditional ISAR imaging under certain limited operating conditions that are nevertheless of practical interest. We conclude by pointing out directions for future work in extending the results of this paper.

I. INTRODUCTION

Inverse Synthetic Aperture Radar (ISAR) imaging, which refers to the formation of images of moving targets by a stationary radar, is potentially a very important tool for both military and civilian applications. The principle manner in which ISAR differs from SAR imaging lies in the fact that the motion of the target to be imaged is unknown. This fact necessitates a motion compensation (MC) algorithm that transforms the data to make it amenable to stationary time-series analysis [1].

Due to the complexities of the target motion dynamics, however, errors in target motion estimation can be significant which in turn degrade the quality of the reconstructed image. On the one hand a large observation interval is required to induce a wide enough aperture to enable sufficient Doppler (and hence cross-range) resolution under Fourier analysis; while on the other hand too long an observation interval potentially fosters the errors due to motion compensation. Further complicating matters is the presence of noise in the signal including white Gaussian noise (induced by noise floor of the system coupled with signal losses due to propagation) and interference due to clutter in which the target is immersed. In this paper we focus on the special case of sea clutter under low grazing angles which leads to impulsively distributed time-series [2].

Compressive sensing (CS) [4] is a recent tool that has been widely advocated for reliably inferring signals from sparse measurements. This therefore is of potential interest for ISAR imaging since it opens up the possibility of imaging the target in low CPI (coherent processing intervals) conditions during which the target motion can, to a good approximation, be assumed to be linear. Our goal in this paper is to ascertain the extent to which CS based ISAR algorithm can help in reliably tackling the above issues in comparison to traditional Fourier

based methods of ISAR imaging under varying levels of noise and clutter powers. In doing so we demonstrate the relative advantages of CS and Fourier based ISAR image formation methods. We find that CS ISAR image formation algorithms do offer some advantages over traditional image formation methods in certain limited signaling regimes which can nevertheless be of potential practical interest.

The next section delves into some of the basics of ISAR image formation, our CS based ISAR algorithm, and the sea clutter models that we employ in our analysis. Detailed simulation results are presented in Section 3 together with a summary of our major findings, and finally we conclude in Section 4 with thoughts on future directions stemming from this work.

II. ISAR IMAGING: CS AND FOURIER METHODS

A. Basics of ISAR Imaging

Translational motion of a rigid body, immersed in the beam of the sensing radar antenna, induces the target to expose its different angular aspects from viewpoint of the stationary sensor. In order to extract this pure rotational component of the target motion, the translational motion component is first adjusted by means of a range compensation algorithm which typically involves alignment of the different range profiles (obtained from successive pulse returns) via low-order polynomial fitting and the matching of prominent peaks [1, 3]. This is followed by a phase compensation stage in order to enable analysis via the FFT algorithm [1, 3].

To facilitate analysis, we assume that the translational motion of the target has been effectively factored out via the above pre-processing steps independent of remaining components of the signal processing chain described below. Given this, assume that the coherent processing interval (CPI), with pulse repetition period T , in which the ISAR image is formed, consists of N LFM (linear frequency modulated) modulated pulses of the form:

$$s(\tau) = A(t) \cdot \text{rect}\left(\frac{\tau}{T_p}\right) \cdot \exp\left(j2\pi\left(f_c\tau + \frac{\alpha}{2}\tau^2\right)\right) \quad (1)$$

where, $\tau = t \bmod T$ is the fast time, t is the slow-time, $A(t)$ is the scattering amplitude, f_c is the carrier frequency, α is the chirp rate, T_p denote the time width of the chirp pulse, and $\text{rect}(\cdot)$ denotes a unit rectangular pulse function.

Consider a point scatterer located at coordinates (x, y) , where x is the range location and y is the cross-range location with respect to the radar sensor. Then it follows that the received complex echo signal is given by [3]:

$$s(\tau, t) = A(t) \cdot \text{rect}\left(\frac{\tau}{T_p}\right) \cdot \text{rect}\left(\frac{t}{T_c}\right) \cdot \exp\left\{j2\pi\left[f_c\left(\tau - \frac{2R(t)}{c}\right) + \frac{\alpha}{2}\left(\tau - \frac{2R(t)}{c}\right)^2\right]\right\} \quad (2)$$

where, c is the speed of light, $T_c = N \cdot T$ is the coherent processing duration in which the target is observed, and such that the range of the point scatterer $R(t)$ can be approximated, under far field assumptions, by [1]:

$$R(t) = R_0 + x \cdot \cos\Delta\theta(t) + y \cdot \sin\Delta\theta(t) \quad (3)$$

such that the rotation angle $\Delta\theta(t)$ can be expanded into a Taylor series expansion [1, 3]:

$$\Delta\theta(t) = \theta(t) - \theta_0 \approx \omega t + \frac{1}{2}\gamma t^2 \quad (4)$$

where, R_0 is the range to the center of that target, ω is the rotation rate and γ is the acceleration rate of the target.

After pulse compression, the received signal in equation (2) becomes:

$$s(\tau, t) = A(t) \cdot \text{rect}\left(\frac{t}{T_c}\right) \cdot \text{sinc}\left[T_p \alpha \left(\tau - \frac{2R(t)}{c}\right)\right] \cdot \exp\left(-j4\pi f_c \frac{R(t)}{c}\right) \quad (5)$$

Substituting (3-4) into (5) yields the following approximation of the received signal:

$$s(\tau, t) \approx A(t) \cdot \text{rect}\left(\frac{t}{T_c}\right) \cdot \text{sinc}\left[T_p \alpha \left(\tau - \frac{2R(t)}{c}\right)\right] \cdot \exp\left[-j4\pi f_c \frac{(R_0+x)}{c}\right] \cdot \exp\left[-j2\pi\left(f \cdot t + \frac{1}{2}\beta t^2\right)\right] \quad (6)$$

where, $f = 2y\omega f_c/c = 2y\omega/\lambda$ and $\beta = 2y\gamma f_c/c = 2y\gamma/\lambda$ are the Doppler and Doppler rate respectively.

Now assuming that the source target can be approximated by K scatterers, the signal at range bin $\tau = f_c \frac{(R_0+x)}{c} = \frac{(R_0+x)}{\lambda}$ can be approximated by:

$$s(t) = \sum_{k=1}^K A_k \cdot \text{rect}\left(\frac{t}{T_c}\right) \cdot \exp\left[-j2\pi\left(f_k \cdot t + \frac{1}{2}\beta_k \cdot t^2\right)\right] \quad (7)$$

where $f_k = 2y_k\omega/\lambda$ and $\beta_k = 2y_k\gamma/\lambda$ are the Doppler and Doppler rate contributions, respectively, of the k^{th} scatterer.

Assuming negligible angular acceleration within the CPI, (7) can be simplified by:

$$s(t) = \sum_{k=1}^K A_k \cdot \text{rect}\left(\frac{t}{T_c}\right) \cdot \exp[-j2\pi f_k \cdot t] \quad (8)$$

Finally, as described in Section 1, we assume that our signal model is contaminated by white Gaussian and impulsive noise as follows:

$$s(t) = \sum_{k=1}^K A_k \cdot \text{rect}\left(\frac{t}{T_c}\right) \cdot \exp(-j2\pi f_k t) + n_g(t) + n_c(t) \quad (9)$$

where n_g is white Gaussian noise and n_c is impulsive sea-clutter interference. Given (9) and ISAR image can be formed simply by taking the FFT at each range bin in order to reveal the corresponding cross-range structure.

B. The CS-ISAR Algorithm

We now reformulate the ISAR image reconstruction problem in terms of the following convex program:

First we express equation (9) in vector form: $s(t) = \Phi\theta + n(t)$, where Φ is a dictionary consisting of complex exponentials $\Phi = [\phi_1, \dots, \phi_D]$; where $\phi_k = \exp(-j2\pi \cdot f_d(k) \cdot t)$, $f_d = [1: D]^T \cdot \Delta f_d$, $\Delta f_d = f_r/D$, such that f_r is the pulse repetition rate. The size of the dictionary D is chosen to be equal to the number of the number of pulses N transmitted during the CPI. Given this the reconstruction problem can be expressed as:

$$\min \|\theta\|_1 \quad \text{subject to } b = \Psi s \quad (10)$$

where vector b consists of the measurements we make of signal s with respect to the measurement matrix Ψ which is chosen such that the matrix $A = \Psi\Phi$ satisfies the so-called Restricted Isometry Property (RIP) in compressive sensing [4]. For our choice of dictionary Φ , RIP is satisfied by a Gaussian noise matrix Ψ . In order to solve (2) we employ the Regularized Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (ROMP) algorithm [5] due to its numerical speed and the fact that it gives comparable performance compared to L_1 minimization algorithms such as [6] for our application.

For the purposes of ISAR imaging under far-field conditions, the assumption that target is sparse in the Dirac basis for each range bin is a good one since the extent of the target to be imaged relative to area illuminated in far-field is typically small. Thus a CS based ISAR imaging approach is attractive from the outset since this sparsity assumption is built-in to the inference procedure to solve inverse problem corresponding to (9). In reality, however, we shall find in Section 3 that CS based ISAR method outperforms Fourier based methods primarily for the low to moderate SINR regions below 15dB for all levels of clutter—and especially for the non-ideal MC case (i.e. for the practically relevant case where the motion of the *a priori* target is unknown to the radar).

We finally point out that CS based ISAR processing presented above provides a good benchmark for the performance of noise-based ISAR imaging systems that employ stochastic waveforms inasmuch as the measurement process inherent in CS mimics the correlation of a transmitted noise waveform with the target signal albeit in a non- *in situ* setting. The *in situ* signal scattering process, which is inherent in noise radar, complicates the signal acquisition (due to various physical factors involved in signal transmission and scattering) and the corresponding motion compensation processes. This therefore renders the CS measurement operator employed here as an idealization of the corresponding *in situ* scenario. Nevertheless the performance of CS ISAR imaging as presented in this paper should serve as a useful guide in developing noise-based radar imaging systems.

C. Sea Clutter Model

In this paper we limit ourselves to sea-clutter observed during low grazing angles which, as explained below, is tantamount to constraining the clutter noise to be impulsive in nature. This scenario is nevertheless of significant practical

interest since it pertains to situations where the imaging radar is mounted on a ship or a boat and is conducting surveillance and forming images of the surrounding environment or battlefield.

Sea clutter in low signal to interference environments can mask the ISAR target. For low grazing angles and very fine radar cell resolution areas, the clutter envelope departs significantly from the Rayleigh distribution. In this case, the clutter is said to display spiky behavior and the distribution of the intensity develops a much longer tail relative to the Rayleigh distribution. A variety of distribution models have been proposed to model distribution of the sea clutter amplitude or intensity returns. Among these, the K, Log-Normal and Weibull distributions have been cited frequently and partial success with these models have been reported. From these, the K distribution which is a compound-Gaussian model has been given a phenomenological interpretation. According to this interpretation, the K distribution envelope is a compound distribution consisting of a locally Rayleigh distribution speckle whose mean is modulated by a gamma distribution. In this paper, the K-Clutter model is used to generate synthetic clutter.

The PDF of the K-Distribution is given by [7]:

$$f(x) = \frac{2b}{\Gamma(v)} \left(\frac{bx}{2}\right) K_v(bx)$$

where x denotes the envelope of the sea clutter, v is the shape parameter, b is the scale parameter and $K_v(x)$ is the modified Bessel function of the third kind of order v .

The v for X-band is given by [7]:

$$\log_{10} v = \frac{2}{3} \log_{10}(\varphi) + \frac{5}{8} \log_{10}(A_c) - k_{pol} - \frac{\cos 2\theta}{3}$$

where φ is the grazing angle in degrees, A_c is the radar resolved area, k_{pol} is polarization dependent parameter and θ is the aspect angle with respect to the swell direction.

In this paper, we used the memoryless non-linear transform [7] to induce correlation upon the clutter. A first order Gauss-Markov model is used to correlate IID Gaussian sequences which are subsequently fed to the MNL algorithm in order to obtain correlated K sequences. The range correlation parameter was chosen according to [8] while the time correlation exponential decay parameter was set to 1.5 seconds.

The clutter parameters are tabulated in Table 1. We should note that in the final range-Doppler image, the Doppler bandwidth of the sea clutter is inversely proportional to the correlation time. Also, we kept the clutter to noise ratio (CNR) as a varying parameter since the CNR depends on factors such as transmission power, the reflectivity function and other parameters. This way, on average, the low CNR cases resemble a low sea state value.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

The radar is operating at X-band frequency of 9.5 GHz and utilizing a bandwidth 300 MHz. The transmission waveform is an LFM with a pulse width of 2.5 micro-seconds. The

radar height is 20 meters and the target is 2 nm from the radar, which yields a low grazing angle of 0.3 degrees. The number of pulses on the illuminated scene in the simulation is chosen from the set [16, 32, 64, 256]. The CNR is chosen from values of -20, 0, 20 and 35 dB; and the SINR is set to values of 5, 10, 25, 20 and 30 dB.

We now demonstrate salient features of the relative performance of the CS and Fourier based ISAR imaging algorithms by plotting the variation of both the PSNR (Peak Signal to Noise Ratio) and MAE (Mean Absolute Error) between a ground truth image and the modulus of the processed ISAR images. We employ two different ground truth images in this paper: for the Fourier case we use the corresponding modulus Fourier ISAR image with zero interference and perfect motion compensation; for the CS case, we use a similar image albeit processed via the a CS image formation algorithm described in Section 2-B under zero inference and perfect motion compensation conditions.

Figures 1-6 show the performance of the CS and Fourier based ISAR algorithms under different signaling and motion compensation scenarios. For each CPI (i.e. number of pulses), we show the PSNR and MAE performance under low (-20dB CNR) and high (35dB CNR) clutter regimes. Furthermore each plot shows the performance both when the target motion is known to the radar (ideal MC case) and when it is not (non-ideal MC case).

We first observe that CS based ISAR algorithm outperforms its Fourier counterpart only in the low (around 5dB) to moderate (around 15 dB) SINR cases for the non-ideal MC case. For the ideal MC condition, appreciable advantage of using CS based approach can be observed only above 64 pulses of CPI. Figures 7-8 show examples of this for the Fourier and CS cases respectively and such that SINR=10dB, CNR is -20dB and CPI is 64 pulses.

As we observe in Figures 1-6, the Fourier based approach outperforms CS based approach for all other cases; and especially in the ideal MC condition. Figure 9-12 show a typical Monte-Carlo run of the case where SINR=30dB, CNR=-20dB, CPI=256 pulses and ideal MC condition. Figures 9 and 10 show the ground truth Fourier and CS images respectively; and Figures 11 and 12 show, respectively, the corresponding ISAR formed image. Though it is clear that the Fourier ISAR image matches well with its ground truth, the CS ISAR image does appear cleaner than the corresponding Fourier ISAR image (in terms of background noise) while preserving the major structural aspects of the target. This observation points, in some respects, to the inherent ambiguity in our choice of ground truth images and of our chosen performance metrics. These issues need to be further examined in future work.

Sea clutter has certain interesting effects on ISAR processing. In particular we observe in Figures 2, 4 and 6 that increasing the clutter levels from low (-20dB) to high(35 dB) levels causes a significant degradation in performance of the Fourier ISAR algorithm for the non-ideal MC case, especially in the low (5dB) to moderate (around 20dB) SINR conditions. Though CS ISAR is also effected by clutter, we find that it is in general more immune to clutter variations

than its Fourier counterpart. The reason for this is likely because our CS ISAR algorithm enforces a sparsity constraint on the reconstructed signal.

IV. DISCUSSION

We formulated the ISAR imaging problem in sea clutter in terms of a convex optimization problem that we solved via compressive sensing. We then systematically compared the performance of our CS based ISAR algorithm with a traditional Fourier based ISAR algorithm.

In summary, our CS based ISAR algorithm does offer some advantages over the Fourier approach in certain limited settings (i.e. low SINR conditions etc.) which nevertheless can be of significant practical interest. This still leaves out, of course, the possibility of exploring more robust CS ISAR algorithms that may overcome some of the limitations of our current CS-based approach. Though the Fourier reconstruction method clearly outperforms our CS based approach in most other cases, in many of these cases the CS and Fourier based results are visually very much comparable. As pointed out above, more effort is needed in examining alternative performance metrics coupled with the appropriate ground truth criteria.

Furthermore, our CS-based ISAR imaging approaches demonstrates resilience to both white Gaussian and spiky sea clutter (observed in low grazing angles); especially in situations where the motion of the target being imaged is unknown. Further improvements can be expected by exploring the use of adaptive clutter cancelling algorithms in conjunction with the CS-based ISAR algorithm presented here. This will be a subject of our future work.

What is also particularly appealing is the fact that CS based ISAR methods offer relatively robust performance under low SINR and CPI conditions for the non-ideal MC case. A short CPI condition ensures that the motion dynamics of the target can, to a good approximation, be assumed to be linear. This coupled with the possibility of performing super-resolution based on successive image frames, opens up the possibility of improving the state-of-the-art of current ISAR imaging technologies.

REFERENCES

- [1] V.C. Chen and H. Ling, *Time-Frequency Transforms for Radar Imaging and Signal Analysis*, 1st ed., Artech House, 2002.
- [2] F.E. Nathanson, J. Reilly, and M.N. Cohen, *Radar Design Principles: Signal Processing and the Environment*, 2nd ed., Mc. Graw-Hill Inc., 1991.
- [3] W.G Carrara, R.S. Goodman, and R.M. Majewski, *Apollight Synthetic Aperture Radar: Signal Processing Algorithms*, 1st edition, Artech House, 1995.
- [4] E.J. Candes and T. Tao, "Near Optimal Signal Recovery From Random Projections: Universal Encoding Strategies?," *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, vol. 52, 2006, pp. 5406-5425.
- [5] D. Needell and R. Vershynin, Uniform Uncertainty Principle and signal recovery via Regularized Orthogonal Matching Pursuit, *Foundations of Computational Mathematics* 9 (2009), 317-334.
- [6] M. Grant, S. Boyd, and Y. Ye, CVX: Matlab Software for Disciplined Convex Programming. [online]. Available: <http://www.stanford.edu/~boyd/cvx/>
- [7] K.D. Ward, R.J.A. Tough and S. Watts, *Sea Clutter: scattering, the K distribution and radar performance*, IET Radar, Sonar and Navigation Series 20, 2006.
- [8] S. Watts, 'Cell-averaging CFAR gain in spatially correlated K-distributed sea clutter', *IEE Proc. RSN*, 143(5), October 1996, pp 321-327.

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Sea Clutter Parameters

Sea State	4
Grazing Angle	0.3 deg
Polarization	Horizontal
Wind Direction	Upwind
Time Correlation Coefficient	1.5 seconds
Range Correlation Coefficient	23 Meters
CNR	[-20,0,20,35]

Table 1: Sea Clutter Parameters employed in our simulations

Figure 1: SINR vs. PSNR for CPI=16 pulses, CNR=-20dB, 25dB

Figure 2: SINR vs. MAE for CPI=16 pulses, CNR=-20dB, 25dB

Figure 3: SINR vs. PSNR for CPI=64 pulses, CNR=-20dB, 25dB

Figure 4: SINR vs. MAE for CPI=64 pulses, CNR=-20dB, 25dB

Figure 5: SINR vs. PSNR for CPI=256 pulses, CNR=-20dB, 25dB

Figure 6: SINR vs. MAE for CPI=256 pulses, CNR=-20dB, 25dB

Figure 7: Fourier ISAR Image for CPI=64 pulses

Figure 8: CS ISAR Image for CPI=64 pulses

Figure 9: Fourier Ground-Truth Image

Figure 10: CS Ground-Truth Image

Figure 11: Fourier ISAR Image for CNR=-20dB, SINR=30dB, CPI=256 Pulses

Figure 12: Fourier ISAR Image for CNR=-20dB, SINR=30dB, CPI=256 Pulses